

IRONY AS A UNIVERSAL AUTHOR'S TECHNIQUE IN THE NOVEL "THE CAT'S CRADLE"

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The article investigates the translation of irony used in belles-lettres texts. The semantics of irony consists in replacing a denomination by its opposite. Irony is a transfer, a renaming based upon the direct contrast of two notions: the notion named and the notion meant. There are at least two kinds of irony. The first represents utterances that can have only an ironical. This kind of irony is called by some authors antiphrastic the second variety we can refer the overwhelming majority of utterances which can be understood either literally, or ironically, especially when we deal with written texts.

Irony is a stylistic device through which the interaction of two types of lexical meanings appears in any word: subject-logical and contextual, based on the relation of opposition (inconsistency). Stylistic irony sometimes requires a broad context. The term "irony", as a stylistic device, should not be confused with the common word "irony" denoting a mocking expression. Likewise, irony should not be confused with humor. As you know, humor is such a quality of action or speech that necessarily arouses the feeling of funny. Humor is a psychological phenomenon. Irony doesn't necessarily make you laugh. In the sentence "How clever it is", where the intonation of the whole sentence gives the word clever - the opposite meaning - stupid does not evoke a sense of ridicule. On the contrary, feelings of irritation, discontent, regret, etc. can be expressed here. Humor can use irony as one of its techniques, and in this case, irony will naturally cause laughter. Funny is usually the result of unjustified expectations, some collision of positive and negative. In this sense, irony as a language device has a lot to do with humor. The use of contextual meanings, the opposite of the main subject-logical meanings, is also a kind of collision of positive and negative, and this collision is always unexpected. This is why irony most often evokes a sense of humor. Thus, the main function of irony (although, as indicated above, and not exclusive) is to cause a humorous attitude towards the reported facts and phenomena. Cat's Cradle by Kurt Vonnegut is a satire on the state of world affairs in the 1960's. Vonnegut made a commentary in this book on the tendency of humans to be warlike, belligerent, and shortsighted. The main character of the book, the narrator, is certainly not a protagonist, although the modern reader craves a hero in every story and the narrator in this one is the most likely candidate. Through the narrator's eyes, Vonnegut created a story of [black humor ending](#) in the destruction of the earth.

In the end the entire earth is destroyed, through a seemingly impossible series of coincidences and completely random events, which strangely enough, are all explained adequately by Bokonism. Throughout the story Vonnegut builds up his theme of the pointlessness of life with the aid of satire. One of the main ways this feeling of pointlessness is accomplished is through the use of [irony](#).

In a sense, total irony is even interested in the unhappiness of the surrounding reality: drawing from its troubles the material for its witty murderous verdicts, it freezes any positive aspiration, desire to improve the world, offering nothing in return. So Vonnegut finds himself in an uneasy

relationship with Bokonon. Indeed, on the one hand, Bokonon's "irony without shores" seems to be a correct way of describing the everyday life in crisis, giving rise to the one who adopts it, the feeling of unlimited power over the "crazy crazy crazy world." On the other hand, Vonnegut sees the danger of a purely playful attitude to the world, when the absence of positive guidelines, coupled with an indomitable ironic element, leads to the ironic being alone with emptiness, since everything else is destroyed by his merciless irony.

An example of the irony in the story is the government of San Lorenzo, a small island nation somewhere in the Caribbean. The people in San Lorenzo were utterly hopeless. They have always been this way. San Lorenzo has been throughout history, one of the most unsuccessful and useless place on earth. The people are poor and do not have any motivation at all. The way that they are kept alive at all is by trickery by the government and the holy man Bokonon. The dictator of San Lorenzo and Bokonon were friends who decided to govern San Lorenzo by themselves. Since the people were hopeless and without direction, Bokonon invented his religion and the dictator outlawed it and made practicing any religion other than Christianity punishable by death. All the people on the island had become devout Bokononists, and the struggle between the government and the religion kept them entertained, and therefore alive. While making fun of many things in modern times, Vonnegut is not inclined to interpret the world as a gigantic "nasty anecdote" - a position characteristic of the school of "black humor", which is very active in America in the post-war decades, where critics of Vonnegut have repeatedly written, overlooking the most important feature of his talent: he perceives the troubles and upheavals of mankind as a personal tragedy. "What can humanity hope for," I thought, "if scientists like Felix Honniker give toys like ice-nine to such myopic children, and all of humanity is made of them?" How did the heirs of the scientist dispose of weapons that are deadly for the whole world? Frank bought himself a job, Angela a husband, and Newt "bought a week with a Russian midget."

Evil is represented in Cat's Cradle with a chemical called ice-nine. This chemical is passed from generation to the next within the Hoenikker family. This is much like evil being passed down from generation to the next. This evil can spread easily and will expand uncontrollably, much like the ice nine which spread through the water and froze the oceans and eventually the earth. Evil and cruelty are represented by two objects which destroy. Ice nine, which freezes over earth and killed the majority of people on earth, and the restaurant which never helped the hotel which was in end.

Vonnegut uses simple, childhood toys to shows the basis of religion. A cat's cradle is meaningless, has no structure, and is confusing. The meaning of a cat's cradle makes no sense and this is another reason why Vonnegut uses it. There is no cat and the cradle is very confusing and he relates this to the church. He believes there is no god in religion and the church. He believes there is no god in religion and the church is just filled with stupid rules and confusion. This toy represents the sarcastic, negativity of religion according to him. He uses this cradle in a silly way in Cat s Cradle. Surely one would not want to base reality on this and yet, some people do.

Overall, Vonnegut criticizes disputable topics using irony and satire in the novel Cat's Cradle. The long history and universality of the novel makes it a perfect symbol for all of humanity's varied attempts to structure the world in a meaningful way, including magic, religion, fiction, philosophy, and science. Society has constructed various pillars (science and religion) to

protect us from the unknown. Kurt Vonnegut uses satire to tear these pillars down. The use of humor is key because it grants Vonnegut the ability to discuss the subjects of his choice without losing the interest of his audience. Vonnegut's writing reflects a dark view of humanity which can only be mocked by humor. The humor is not put forward to cover up the serious themes, but, rather, to further them. Vonnegut prevents the reader from warming himself with lies and gives a comical yet ruthless way to bestow upon the reader thoughtfulness. He aims to show society just how backward it's thinking is, and he accomplishes this goal in *Cat's Cradle*.

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